

Effect of Cooling Rate on Mode II Fatigue Crack Growth Behavior in Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polyphenylene Sulfide

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Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP)

Attention given to cycle time, material storage, toughness, recyclability, etc.

Aerospace applications → PPS, PAEK family (PEEK, PEKK, etc.)

Polyphenylene Sulfide (PPS)

- Crystalline
- High specific strength and toughness
- Relatively inexpensive
- Excellent thermal stability
- Excellent moisture and chemical resistance

[1] Tenney et al. NASA/CR-2011-217076 (2011)

CF/PPS application in aircraft

Excerpt from [2] Table A-II Flying structural parts made of thermoplastic composites (TPC).

Description	Manufacturer	Manufacturing Process	Date	Notes
Airbus 340 wing leading edge access panels	GKN Fokker	Co-consolidated.	2002	
Airbus A350 brackets	GKN Fokker	Stamp formed clips and cleats bolted to skins and frames.	2002	The Airbus 350-XWB has over 8,000 TPC brackets.
Boeing 787 brackets	Dahar		2014	Over 10,000 per aircraft.
Fokker 50 main landing gear doors	GKN Fokker	Assembled with Resistive welding.		
Leonardo (AgustaWestland) AW169 helicopter horizontal tail leading edge	GKN Fokker	Two omega sections butted between flat skins to produce a full span torsion box.	2018	JEC 2013 innovation award. 15% lighter than previous design.
Airbus 340-600 ribs and angle brackets	GKN Fokker			Used on keel beam and ailerons.

CF/PPS has **high demand** in terms of high-rate production and weight reduction.

[2] Krueger et al. NASA/TM-20240005376 (2024)

CFRTP manufacturing: Hot press molding

Material placed in mold → Heating & Pressing → Cooling (Consolidation)

- High molding temperature

 - Large mismatch in thermal expansion between the base material and the fibers

- In the case of crystalline resin: Thermal shrinkage + Volumetric shrinkage due to crystallization

 - Large thermal residual stress

Crystallinity changes depending on **cooling rate**

Cooling rate

Crystallinity

Mechanical Properties, Fracture Behavior

Purpose

Elucidation of cooling rate dependence of basic properties in CF/PPS composite materials

Our Previous study: Evaluation of Thermal, Mechanical, and Fracture Properties of PPS and CF/PPS

Today's Content

Mode II Fatigue Fracture Characterization of CF/PPS
(ENF Fatigue Test, Fracture Surface Observation)

- CFRTP Specimen

CF/PPS unidirectional prepreg sheet (TenCate Cetex® TC1100, Toray)

(Carbon fiber; AS4, $V_f = 59 \text{ vol\%}$)

→ CF/PPS laminate $[0_{12} // 0_{12}]$

- Hot press molding: 325 °C, 20 min

- Cooling rate during consolidation: **1, 5, 10 °C/min**

- Characterization of mode II fatigue crack propagation

→ End-notched flexure (ENF) fatigue test

- Preliminary experiments for parameter setting

Static loading while changing initial crack position a

→ Calculation compliance C at each crack position a

→ Relationship between crack length a - compliance C

$$(2h)^3 B C = \beta_0 + a^3 \beta_1 \quad (h: \text{thickness, } B: \text{width } \beta_0, \beta_1: \text{constant})$$

For fatigue test, setting crack length a and energy release rate G_{\max} and determine P_{\max}

$$G_{\max} = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} = \frac{P_{\max}^2}{2B^2} \frac{3a^2}{(2h)^3} \beta_1 \quad (\text{Modified Compliance Calibration Method})$$

- Fatigue test
 - Fatigue testing machine: Electropuls E10000 (Instron)
 - Load ratio: $R = 0.1 (P_{\max} / P_{\min})$
 - Frequency: 10 Hz
 - Sampling interval: 5 ms (20 points / wave)
 - Load gradation test method ($\times 0.99$, 5 to 10 times / test)

Calculation of compliance C for each cycle, and crack length a corresponding to C

→ Calculation of G_{\max} for each cycle

→ Setting ΔN at which the average R^2 value of G_{\max} is greater than 0.90

→ Plotting fatigue crack propagation characteristics ($da/dN - G_{\max}$ diagram)

$$G_{\max} = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} = \frac{P_{\max}^2}{2B^2} \frac{3a^2}{(2h)^3} \beta_1 \quad (\text{Modified Compliance Calibration Method})$$

Fatigue crack propagation characteristics ($da/dN - G_{max}$ diagram)

- Cooling rate 10, 5 °C/min ($G_{max} = 0.1 \sim 0.5 \text{ kJ/m}^2$)

Proportional relationship between da/dN and G_{max} on both logarithmic graphs (Paris law)

→ Behavior following the Paris law until around $da/dN = 10^{-10} \text{ m/cycle}$

→ Fatigue crack growth threshold is not clear.

Fatigue crack propagation characteristics ($da/dN - G_{max}$ diagram)

- Cooling rate 1 °C/min ($G_{max} = 0.3 \sim 0.6 \text{ kJ/m}^2$)

Proportional relationship between da/dN and G_{max} on both logarithmic graphs (Paris law)

Fatigue crack growth stops at around $G_{max} = 0.26 \text{ kJ/m}^2 \rightarrow$ Fatigue crack growth threshold

1 °C/min is particularly variable (Large crystal size \rightarrow Fracture might dominate local properties)

(Crystallinity, Static fracture toughness test) Oshima et al. *Composites Part A* 164 (2023)

- Lower cooling rate → **Higher crystallinity** and **lower fracture toughness**
(Reasonable results considering the properties of thermoplastic resins)
- G_{IIC} : **Equivalent at 5 and 10 °C/min**, lower and more variable at 1 °C/min

Fatigue crack propagation characteristics ($da/dN - G_{max}$ diagram)

- Plot value and slope: **Equivalent at 5 and 10 °C/min**, lower and more variable at 1 °C/min

→ Trends consistent with static test results

- **Lower cooling rate → Crack propagation rate (da/dN) decreased**

(The large slope at 1 °C/min corresponds to the **low toughness** in the static test region (higher G_{max}))

Fatigue crack propagation characteristics ($da/dN - G_{max}$ diagram)

This suggests a possible transition in fracture mode between 5 °C/min and 1 °C/min.

→ The region of **significant change in crystallization behavior**

(→ Discussed later in fracture surface observation)

Fracture Surface (SEM Image)

【Higher G_{max} 】
 $da/dN = 10^{-6}$

【Lower G_{max} 】
 $da/dN = 10^{-9}$
 ※1 °C/min: 10^{-8}

CF/Epoxy [3]
 $da/dN = 10^{-7}$

- **Ductile fracture of PPS matrix** observed throughout (Brittle fracture of epoxy: hackle pattern)
- Small effect of cooling rate on fracture morphology

[3] Hojo et al. *Int J Fatigue* 28 (2006)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fracture Surface (SEM Image)

(Small Difference)

[2] Oshima et al. (2023)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fracture Surface (SEM Image)_Enlarged View

【Higher G_{max} 】
 $da/dN = 10^{-6}$

【Lower G_{max} 】
 $da/dN = 10^{-9}$

※1 °C/min: 10^{-8}

CF/Epoxy [3]
 $da/dN = 10^{-7}$

- Higher G_{max} Exposed carbon fiber \blacktriangleright (low interface strength)
- Lower G_{max} Resin elongated significantly \blacktriangledown in 10, 5 °C/min

Influence of cooling rate appears at lower G_{max}

[3] Hojo et al. *Int J Fatigue* 28 (2006)

Comparison with another polymer matrix

Fig. 14. Relation between crack propagation rate and maximum energy release rate under mode II loading for base and 50 μm -epoxy-interleaved laminates.

[3] Hojo et al. *Int J Fatigue* 28 (2006)

Compare with conventional **CF/Epoxy [3]** ...

- CF/PPS: Lower da/dN and Higher G_{max}

→ CF/PPS has higher resistance

to fatigue crack propagation than CF/Epoxy

Comparison with another polymer matrix

[4] Martin et al. *NASA TECHNICAL MEMORANDUM* 100577 (1988)

Compare with **CF/PEEK** [4] ...

- Value: Close to CF/PEEK
 - Slope: CF/PEEK < CF/PPS (easier crack propagation)
- **CF/PPS is inferior to CF/PEEK fatigue resistance**
- ∴ Interface properties, trans-crystal formation

Prospects of CF/PPS

Improvement of performance

by modifying fiber-base material interface

e.g. resin modification, CF surface treatment, molding process improvement, etc.

Influence of Cooling Rate on Fatigue Damage Mechanisms in CF/PPS Composites

- ✓ **Lower cooling rate → Lower crack growth rate**

Cooling rate 10, 5 °C/min → No clear fatigue crack growth threshold

Cooling rate 1 °C/min → Fatigue crack growth threshold around $G_{\max} = 0.26 \text{ kJ/m}^2$

- ✓ Fracture surface → Ductile fracture of PPS matrix

Influence of cooling rate on fracture morphology appears at lower G_{\max}

- ✓ Resistance to fatigue crack propagation

CF/Epoxy << CF/PPS < CF/PEEK